

e-SAFE

**CHANGING THE
LANDSCAPE OF EU
NON-HISTORICAL
BUILDING STOCK**

e-SAFE EEIG*

Future-Proofing Buildings

Born from EU Innovation. Built for Lasting Impact.

The e-SAFE EEIG is a European collaboration created to replicate and scale the success of the EU Horizon 2020 e-SAFE project - a pioneering initiative that combines energy efficiency, seismic resilience, and circular economy principles in a single, scalable solution.

Our integrated approach helps transform non-historic buildings (such as schools, public housing, public facilities, residential blocks, and offices) into safer, greener, more beautiful, and longer-lasting assets - without requiring occupant relocation or generating excessive material waste.

While our technologies can be applied broadly, they are particularly effective for reinforced concrete buildings constructed before the introduction of EU standards for seismic safety and energy performance.

* European Economic Interest Group

WHY e-SAFE?

We deliver value across public and private sectors by addressing today's most urgent renovation needs:

PUBLIC AUTHORITIES

Improve climate performance, reduce risk exposure, and extend the value of public assets.

ARCHITECTS & ENGINEERS

Use modular, high-performance prefabricated components that simplify complex retrofits.

PUBLIC HOUSING & SCHOOLS

Renovate with speed, minimal disruption, and measurable impact for vulnerable communities.

CITIZENS

Benefit from safer, more comfortable, and energy-efficient living and learning environments.

A Circular, Resilient Approach to Renovation

e-SAFE is designed for sustainability in every sense. Our approach contributes to the circular economy by:

- Using timber and other sustainable and recycled/recyclable materials
- Preserving existing buildings through non-destructive retrofit techniques
- Extending lifespan, safety, comfort, and efficiency
- Reducing construction waste and resource use
- Supporting modular upgrades that adapt over time

By deep renovating what already exists, we avoid unnecessary demolition and support a more resilient and regenerative building stock.

Tailored for Schools, Public Housing & Public Facilities

Public buildings face high expectations and tight constraints. e-SAFE helps you meet them all:

- Fast and low-disruption renovations, ideal for occupied schools and housing
- Compliance with EU energy and seismic regulations
- Reduced operating costs and carbon footprint
- Enhanced comfort and air quality for users
- Improved architectural image
- Long-term resilience against earthquakes, energy shocks, and climate change

WHAT WE OFFER

We don't sell off-the-shelf products - we deliver comprehensive, integrated renovation solutions:

- ❑ e-SAFE model application in new countries and regions
- ❑ Co-development of large-scale renovation projects
- ❑ Technical support, capacity-building, and stakeholder training
- ❑ Acceleration of market uptake for innovative, low-carbon technologies

Our Core Technologies

Each system is designed to improve energy performance, structural safety, and building resilience, while being cost-effective and scalable:

e-CLT

Cross-laminated timber walls with built-in seismic dampers for dual safety and sustainability.

C-PANEL

Prefabricated timber panels combining insulation, high performing windows, and modern finishes.

C-EXOS

Modular steel exoskeletons to strengthen seismic performance and add architectural value.

e-THERM

Integrated energy systems for heating, cooling, and hot water, powered by renewables.

e-TANK

Compact and efficient hot water storage tailored for hybrid energy systems.

e-BEMS

A building energy management system to monitor, control, and optimize comfort and energy use.

e-DSS

A digital decision-support tool to guide planning and ensure tailored, high-impact outcomes.

YOUR BENEFITS

Partnering with the e-SAFE Innovation Partnership means you get:

- ✔ Up to 90% energy savings
- ✔ Significantly enhanced seismic resilience
- ✔ Fast and cost-effective renovations with minimal disruption
- ✔ Better indoor comfort and air quality
- ✔ Extended building life and reduced environmental impact
- ✔ Alignment with EU Green Deal and circular economy goals

Proven, Measurable Impact

Up to 90% reduction in primary energy use

Up to 90% reduction in CO₂ emissions

Time and cost savings through prefabrication

Up to 100% improvement in seismic resistance

Less construction waste, longer building lifespan

From Research to Real-World Change

The e-SAFE Horizon 2020 project proved that it's possible to combine deep renovation, affordability, seismic safety, and circularity in one system.

Now, through the e-SAFE EEIG, we're bringing this model to life-helping cities, housing agencies, and building owners all over Europe build a resilient, sustainable future.

The e-SAFE is legally established as a European Economic Interest Grouping (EEIG), enabling cross-border collaboration to scale impact throughout the EU.

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